

If you are a computer programmer, there isn't a reason for why you shouldn't write a website with tips and tutorials on how you use a particular computer language to accomplish a specific goal.

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Sometimes people underestimate what they already know and that often leads to seeking that "secret" knowledge. The logic is as follows: If someone is not making any money online, it must be that they don't know what it takes to make [money](#).